

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL TAX SYSTEMS IN THE TAXATION OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES

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Abstract

Cryptocurrency taxation is a set of taxes on cryptocurrencies in a particular jurisdiction that are levied on various transactions conducted by legal entities and individuals with cryptocurrencies. Questions about the legal nature of digital currency and transactions are handled differently in each country. Various jurisdictions treat digital currency as a means of payment or, more broadly, as a medium of exchange. The lack of formal certainty in this area regarding the general legal status of cryptocurrencies entails extensive discussions on more specific issues regarding the need for licensing the activities of exchanges, taxation of cryptocurrencies, and so on. The situation is constantly changing. Ordinary users often fear that if they encounter problems when working with cryptocurrency exchanges or ICOs, they may not receive help from the state and support from the law. Miners and traders also remain at risk, worried about the uncertainty of the cryptocurrency tax on income generation. It should be remembered here that mining, as a type of activity, requires an initial investment and the regular purchase of new computer components, and is currently not protected by law. Trading crypto assets is similar in nature to trading stocks and securities. The approach to be taken in determining whether a transaction is taking place or not is also similar, and guidance can be drawn from existing jurisprudence in stock and securities trading. The capital gains tax for cryptocurrencies works the same as for other assets: if a loss is incurred in transactions, you can declare a loss and save on fiscal deductions. There are two different types of capital gains taxes: long term and short term. Long term means you held the currency for more than a year before selling or trading it, short term applies to less than a year. Rates vary by country and taxpayer category.

Keywords: Cryptocurrency, taxation, assets, transaction, financial, fiscal.

The widespread introduction of new digital information technologies in the financial sector has led to the emergence of a new class of assets in payment systems and financial markets - crypto assets (crypto-assets) or virtual assets (virtual assets), which are commonly called digital financial assets. Examples of such assets are virtual currencies, stablecoins, and other digital tokens. Digital financial assets can perform various financial functions, since they include assets of different economic and legal nature: cash, equity, debt, etc. At the same time, all these assets are combined into one class by the fact that they are created using distributed ledger technology (distributed ledger technology) or blockchain (blockchain). The distributed ledger technology allows storing all information related to the issue, trading or transfer of financial assets in a decentralized manner. (4)

According to the classification of crypto assets adopted in a number of countries (Great Britain, Switzerland, USA, etc.), modern crypto assets, depending on the nature of the digital tokens used, can be divided into three main types: payment tokens (exchange tokens); security tokens (tokens as digital analogues of securities); utility tokens. Payment tokens in the economic literature are synonymous with virtual currencies. (12) They are not issued or maintained by any central authority or monetary authority and are intended to be used as a medium of exchange or means of payment. Security tokens are the digital equivalent (in terms of rights and obligations) of traditional investment instruments such as stocks or bonds. Utility tokens provide

holders with access to a current or future product or service of the issuing company, but do not give holders the right to own shares in the company or to interest income.

Unlike security tokens, which are usually taxed by similar traditional investment instruments, as well as utility tokens, transactions with which are most often tax-free, the taxation of virtual currencies is the most differentiated by country. In addition, despite the wide range of digital financial assets, virtual currencies (cryptocurrencies) play the most significant role among them, both in terms of capitalization and the number of transactions. Thus, virtual currencies today can act not only as a means of payment or a means of exchange, but also as a store of value and an object of investment⁴. For these reasons, the study of taxation issues of virtual currencies is currently of the greatest scientific interest.

From a functional point of view, virtual currency can be defined as a digital expression of value that can be bought and sold digitally and function as: 1) a medium of exchange; and/or 2) unit of account; and/or 3) a store of value. However, it does not have legal status in any jurisdiction (i.e. it is not legal tender from a regulatory point of view in most developed and developing countries). From the point of view of the institutional approach, virtual currency can be interpreted as a digital expression of value, which is issued by non-traditional issuers of modern forms of money - the Central Bank, credit institutions or specialized issuers of electronic money, but at the same time can be used to a limited extent as an alternative to generally recognized

forms of money in settlements in electronic networks (16).

Most digital financial assets do not sufficiently perform standard monetary functions and, from the point of view of banking regulators, are not absolutely safe to use as a medium of exchange⁵. So, for example, virtual currencies differ in a number of essential characteristics both from generally recognized national fiduciary money issued by state monetary authorities, and from electronic money issued by credit institutions or specialized issuers. (15)

The essential features of virtual currencies are as follows.

1) Trust mechanism of value formation. Virtual currencies are assets whose value is determined by supply and demand, like gold. However, unlike goods, they have zero intrinsic value. As a result, their value is based only on the belief that they can be exchanged for other goods, services, or a certain amount of national currency at a later point in time.

2) Ensuring direct exchange of electronic value. Until recently, in the direct exchange of goods between the parties without the participation of intermediaries, only cash could be used in the calculations. The key innovation of virtual currency schemes is the use of distributed ledger technology, which guarantees the remote exchange of value in the absence of trust between the parties and without the participation of intermediaries.

3) An institutional mechanism in which the management of information and financial transactions is carried out without the participation of intermediaries. Most virtual currency schemes are not run by any particular person or institution. This distinguishes them from electronic money systems that have one or more issuers of value that are subject to the obligation to refund the electronic money. The decentralized nature of most virtual currencies implies the absence of any identifiable scheme operators, which are usually credit institutions or specialized issuers in the case of electronic money. (17)

A steady increase in interest in the development of the circulation of virtual currencies was observed in

2014–2015. This interest was dictated by the payment and investment potential of virtual currencies. As a result, during 2016-2017 exchange rates of virtual currencies have steadily increased, leading to a record total cryptocurrency market capitalization of \$813.87 billion in early 2018. (9) However, problems with the speed of transactions and rising mining costs contributed to a sharp drop in the price of major cryptocurrencies in 2018.

The deep correction of the virtual currency market, as a result of which the total capitalization of cryptocurrencies decreased by 80% from January 2018 to December 2018, was also associated with spontaneous actions of regulators. For example, improvements in regulations in countries such as the US, Japan, and South Korea in 2018 dampened speculative activity in the virtual currency market. (24) At the same time, one of the most important problems hindering the widespread use of virtual currencies in the payment and investment sphere, both by private payers and investors and institutional players, is still the lack of a comprehensive economic and legal framework for regulating digital financial assets. The timeliness of the introduction of regulatory mechanisms in the tax area of digital financial assets as one of the most important tools of state regulation is due to the high interest in virtual currencies on the part of financial market participants and regulatory authorities.

Despite a significant decline in the capitalization of most crypto assets in 2018, the number of assets and the value of transactions using them continued to grow. Thus, the volume of transactions in the Bitcoin network in 2018 exceeded \$ 3.3 trillion, which is six times more than the payment system PayPal, and 16.5 times more than Western Union. Since May 2019, there has been an increase in the capitalization of leading crypto assets and an increase in trading volumes. For example, the daily trading volume of Bitcoin in March 2019 exceeded \$11 billion, which was the most significant figure in the 24-hour period since April 2017. (23) Table 1 shows the leading crypto assets by market capitalization.

Table 1.

Leading crypto assets in the world by capitalization in 2022

Name of crypto asset	Crypto asset classification	Volume in circulation, million units currencies	Capitalization, mln USD
Bitcoin	BTC	19 421 718 BTC	\$587,414,185,982
Ethereum	ETH	120 214 105 ETH *	\$225,858,077,654
Tether	USDT	83 355 853 919 USDT *	\$83,346,736,209
BNB	BNB	155 850 313 BNB *	\$36,560,491,274
USD Coin	USDC	27 501 448 989 USDC *	\$27,500,072,235
XRP	XRP	52 254 289 650 XRP *	\$24,464,249,761
Cardano	ADA	34 955 839 721 ADA *	\$9,870,661,982
Dogecoin	DOGE	140 065 456 384 DOGE	\$9,228,170,998
Solana	SOL	401 308 452 SOL *	\$8,263,251,145
Litecoin	LTC	73 303 839 LTC	\$7,146,482,812

Source: (9)

In 2022, there were more than 2,400 crypto assets in circulation with a capitalization of more than \$296.72 billion. The virtual currency Bitcoin⁹ accounted for more than 62% of the total capitalization of crypto assets. At the same time, the first 10 crypto assets (nine were digital coins, one was a digital token) accounted for about 87.5% of the market capitalization, which indicates a high concentration of funds in the most reliable digital assets. The largest crypto assets in terms of capitalization in 2022 were: Bitcoin, Ethereum, XRP, Bitcoin Cash, Bitcoin SV, Litecoin, etc. (22) (Table 1).

At the same time, despite the fact that Bitcoin is the most capitalized virtual currency on the market, the ratio of daily trading volume to network capitalization for this currency is not the highest and is about 0.14%, while for other leading virtual currencies, such as Litecoin, EOS, Bitcoin Cash and Ethereum, it is higher at 0.67%, 0.41%, 0.39% and 0.36% respectively. (1) This indicates that Bitcoin is currently used mainly not as a means of payment, but as a store of value and investment asset due to the great confidence in it from market participants.

Currently, the market of crypto assets is at the initial stage of development, and there is every reason to believe that in the coming years, the importance of crypto assets both in payment systems and in financial markets will increase as volatility decreases, the scope and directions of the legal use of crypto assets expand, and the speed of processing transactions using them. At the same time, one of the most important problems preventing the active legal use of virtual currencies in the payment and investment sphere by private users and organizations (credit institutions and investment funds) is the lack of clear economic and legal regulation of crypto assets in most national jurisdictions.

If in 2017-2018 (against the background of the first cryptocurrency boom) states were at the origins of adapting their tax systems to the challenges posed by cryptocurrencies, by the beginning of the 2020s, many governments had already enshrined the relevant norms and concepts in tax legislation and were actively applying them. on practice. (19)

Currently, we can talk, with some reservations, about the existence of three concepts of general legal regulation of cryptocurrencies:

1) a complete ban and criminalization of the circulation of cryptocurrencies. Signs of this approach can be found in China, where from 2021 any transactions with cryptocurrencies are recognized as illegal and entail administrative or criminal liability;

2) strict regulation of the circulation of cryptocurrencies implies their recognition as an element of civil circulation (property), however, establishes a strict framework for their use and does not allow their use as a means of payment for goods or services. Representatives of this approach include the Russian legal system, in which cryptocurrencies are categorized as digital currency;

3) the expanded use of cryptocurrencies can be defined as their simultaneous recognition both as property and as a means of payment. The United States is per-

haps one of the most prominent adherents of this concept. So, as of the end of 2020, more than 2,300 American companies accepted bitcoin as payment for goods or services. (21)

Any application of the comparative legal method implies the existence of a system of criteria by which comparison is made and to which, in a certain sense, certain elements of the legal system (or systems) are brought. The legal structure of the tax as a central element of the tax system of any state largely reflects the general approach of the legislator to the tax and legal regulation of a particular object of public relations.

The OECD classification of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development distinguishes the following groups of taxes according to the principle of the object of taxation:

- 1) taxes on income, profits and capital gains;
- 2) social security contributions;
- 3) taxes on payroll and workforce;
- 4) taxes on property;
- 5) taxes on goods and services;
- 6) other taxes. (3)

It is worth noting that this division is only slightly different from that presented in the IMF manual on public finance statistics: instead of group 5 (taxes on goods and services), the international financial regulator distinguishes two categories: national taxes on goods and services (English domestic taxes on goods and services) and taxes on international trade and transactions.

The above OECD classification will be used further to characterize the existing cryptocurrency taxation rules in various jurisdictions.

Jurisdictions for our article were chosen in accordance with the following features: the absence of a ban on the civil circulation of cryptocurrencies; belonging to the Romano-Germanic (Netherlands, Germany, Portugal) or Anglo-Saxon (USA, Singapore) legal family; world leadership in the number of companies operating in the field of blockchain technologies (USA, Singapore, Germany); the presence of special approaches to the taxation of cryptocurrencies (Netherlands). In addition, it is important to note that the main subject of this study is the tax legal relations of individuals arising in connection with the commission of cryptocurrency purchase and sale transactions.

The legal regulation of cryptocurrency in the United States of America is carried out both at the federal level and at the state level. At the same time, if in the first case the main authors of the new norms are the executive authorities (the Securities Commission, the Internal Revenue Service, etc.), which discreetly recognize the importance of recognizing crypto assets for the development of the country's economy, then among the states, two approaches to regulation of cryptocurrency turnover: stimulating (Wyoming, Ohio, Colorado) and restrictive (Iowa, New York). At the same time, it is worth noting that both at the federal level and in most states, there is currently no narrow and unified definition of cryptocurrency, which allows for ad hoc regulation in a dynamically changing and developing blockchain technology environment. (2)

Despite the presence of abundant material on the regulation of cryptocurrencies by state legislatures, for the purposes of this article, we will be limited to the experience of federal tax and legal regulation. So, the U.S. Internal Revenue Service qualifies cryptocurrencies as property, not as currency, for tax purposes. In addition, the tax authority warns of the need to keep records of all transactions with cryptoassets and clarifies when so-called taxable events on capital gains and income taxes for both individuals and companies occur. At the same time, it should be noted that both of these taxes correspond to the extended group of income taxes in accordance with the OECD classification.

So, in the case of an individual selling cryptocurrency for fiat money, as well as using it to purchase goods and services or exchange it for another crypto asset, a positive financial result will be subject to capital gains tax. At the same time, the amount of the tax will largely depend on the period of ownership of the cryptocurrency prior to its implementation: if such a period is less than 1 year, the tax is calculated in accordance with standard income tax rates; if the holding period exceeded a year, the tax rate will be 0%, 15% or 20% depending on the status of the taxpayer. (5) Separately, it is worth noting the existing mechanisms for balancing the financial result, as well as accounting for and carrying forward losses in the current and future periods, respectively, which provides transactions with cryptocurrency with the same rights as transactions with other, more traditional, assets within the framework of capital gains tax (for example, with shares of public companies).

In addition, the IRS highlights other events that give rise to obligations to pay income tax. These include, in particular, the free receipt of cryptocurrency (as a result of the so-called marketing campaigns, called airdrops); interest income from cryptocurrency loans (for example, through decentralized lending protocols - DeFi lending protocols); receiving cryptocurrency in the form of income from mining, as well as staking cryptocurrency and placing it in liquidity pools; receiving cryptocurrency in the form of payment for work (for example, as a reward for developers for finding technical vulnerabilities and imperfections in the program code, called a bug bounty). (20)

Special attention deserves the use of a tax deduction called the "Bernie Madoff deduction" in honor of the creator of one of the largest financial pyramids in the history of the world. Its mechanism provides for the possibility of deducting the full cost of losses incurred by an investor as a result of participation in a pyramid scheme or other fraudulent scheme, which is often found in the unsettled cryptocurrency market. At the same time, it should be noted that in order to confirm this deduction, it is necessary to have a formal accusation of a specific person in fraud, which entailed the loss of funds by the taxpayer.

The Netherlands stands out among other countries with a special approach to the taxation of cryptocurrency, defining it as an asset and imposing a direct tax on its owners - individuals, the amount of which depends not on the actual income received from the use

of the asset, but on the value of the asset at the beginning of the year. Such a tax actually has the nature of property taxes in accordance with the OECD classification, and it is worth noting that before the tax reform of 2001 it was such, being a separately levied tax on wealth (*Vermogensbelasting*). (7)

Currently, the taxation rules used in it are incorporated into the income tax law, which, nevertheless, does not level its nature (according to which the basis of taxation is the fact of owning an asset): the taxpayer indicates the value of cryptocurrency assets at the beginning of the year, on the basis of which it is calculated imputed income, which is then taxed at a rate of 31%. At the same time, if the taxpayer's operations with cryptocurrencies are of a professional nature (for example, he is engaged in their purchase and sale on a daily basis), then the actual income from such activities will be taxed.

Companies trading or mining cryptocurrencies in the Netherlands are required to pay corporation tax on their profits (income minus expenses). At the same time, if an organization or entrepreneur sells goods or services for cryptocurrency, then such income is converted into the national currency (euro) and taken into account as part of total income.

In Germany, cryptocurrencies have received the status of so-called private property. In accordance with the tax legislation of the country, such an asset cannot be accepted as payment for goods or services, and the income from its sale by an individual is not taxable if the amount of profit was less than 600 euros or the asset was owned by the taxpayer for more than one year. (6) At the same time, income from the sale of cryptocurrency is subject to income tax if less than one year has passed since its acquisition, and the amount of profit exceeded the threshold. The taxpayer has the right to reduce the tax base by the amount of expenses incurred (including the acquisition amount and, for example, the stock exchange commission), and the total amount of tax is calculated according to the rates in accordance with the progressive taxation scale in force in Germany.

German business pays income tax in case of transactions with cryptocurrencies, by analogy with individuals, with one significant caveat: the period of ownership of an asset before the sale does not matter for corporate taxpayers - all income received by them is subject to taxation. In addition, income from the sale of cryptocurrencies also forms the tax base for the tax on commercial activities (*Gewerbesteuer*).

Portugal stands out from other European countries with one of the most liberal approaches to the legal regulation of cryptocurrency turnover in general and its taxation in particular. Thus, the tax authority of the country (*port. Autoridade e Aduaneira*) issued clarifications regarding the taxation of operations with cryptocurrency, according to which individuals are exempted from paying taxes in the event that cryptocurrency is sold in exchange for fiat money or another cryptocurrency (against the backdrop of the current tax on capital gains from operations with financial instruments). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that this rule applies strictly to operations for the purchase and sale

of cryptocurrencies that are not related to regular activities and are not the main occupation of the taxpayer - an individual. Otherwise, the income received from such operations is classified as business income and is subject to personal income tax (port. Imposto sobre o Rendimento das Pessoas Singulares). Similarly, any income from cryptocurrency transactions received by organizations is subject to taxation - they are subject to corporate income tax (port. Imposto sobre o Rendimento de Pessoas Coletivas). (10)

Special attention deserves the fact that the act of the main tax authority of the country discussed above is actually the only public regulatory source containing the rules for taxing cryptocurrency. At the same time, it is worth noting the mechanism of clarifications provided for by the Portuguese tax legislation on the appeals of taxpayers. Such clarifications are issued by the tax authority in order to eliminate uncertainty, are mandatory and are valid for four years from the date of issue.

Singapore has a rich and at the same time relatively liberal approach to cryptocurrency regulation. Despite the fact that the authorities of the country do not recognize the decentralized currency as legal tender, they allow its circulation in business activities. At the same time, it should be noted that such activities are subject to mandatory licensing or obtaining an independent examination for compliance of such activities with state legislation. If cryptocurrencies are used by companies as a means of payment for goods or services, then such a transaction is recognized as a barter transaction (a digital asset is qualified by analogy with real estate), and the sale value converted into national currency is subject to general corporate income tax rules.

If the activity of buying and selling cryptocurrencies is systematic (entrepreneurial) in nature, then in this case the financial result is qualified by the tax authorities of the country as profit and will be subject to income tax. At the same time, in the case of an irregular (investment) nature of the sale of cryptocurrency, it qualifies as capital and will not be taxed, since there is no taxation of capital gains in the country.

There are no special laws for cryptocurrency in Azerbaijan. The Minister of Finance of the country, Nijat Imanov, made a statement at the FIF-2018 forum in Baku that now all transactions with digital assets are taxed. During his speech, he mentioned that the new rule applies to individuals and legal entities.

It turns out that cryptocurrency holders must pay income tax. For example, an investor bought bitcoin (BTC) for \$35,000 and sold it for \$40,000. It is for this income of \$5,000 that you need to pay tax. (13)

In 2018, the Center for the Study and Development of the Cryptocurrency Market and Blockchain Technology under the Central Bank was also opened in Azerbaijan. This is another step towards the regulation of digital assets in the country.

Despite the fact that the first steps to control cryptocurrencies were made in 2018, by 2022, no legislation has been created to regulate them.

As mentioned above, cryptocurrency transactions are taxed as income. You also need to pay a commission from the bank in the amount of 10%. To this

amount you need to add an additional payment for the operation of the exchange.

Thus, cryptocurrency holders in Azerbaijan pay tax as follows:

- income tax. Individuals pay 14% of the amount up to AZN 2.5 thousand or \$25 of the amount over AZN 2.5 thousand (approximately \$1,470). Legal entities pay 20%;

- commission to banks in the amount of 10%. The fact is that the purchase of cryptocurrency is regarded as a transfer to a foreign resident. This transfer is taxable;

- exchange commissions. You need to pay an additional fee for buying and selling cryptocurrency. (15)

It turns out that the tax on cryptocurrency in Azerbaijan is at least 24%, which is quite a high figure.

Some analysts in Azerbaijan are critical of the local cryptocurrency taxation system. For example, economist Asiman Guliyev believes that it is she who slows down the spread of digital assets in the country. (14)

According to TripleA data for 2021, in Azerbaijan, 1% of the population owns cryptocurrency. This is approximately 98 thousand people. (16)

Economist Rashad Hasanov believes that there are several factors that influence the slow development of cryptocurrency in Azerbaijan. First, investments in general are not in demand in the country. It turns out that the population does not have basic knowledge about trading instruments and markets. Secondly, people do not trust new technologies. Thirdly, companies that are associated with cryptocurrency are not engaged in education in the country.

There is no special legislation for cryptocurrency in Azerbaijan. Holders of digital assets pay income tax.

Consideration of the experience of tax and legal regulation of cryptocurrency turnover in various jurisdictions (including through the prism of international standards in the field of state tax policy) allows us to draw a number of significant conclusions regarding the legal approaches to cryptocurrency taxation existing in the world.

First of all, it should be noted that in the vast majority of the considered jurisdictions, there is currently no strictly defined interpretation of the term "cryptocurrency" and related concepts, which seems quite justified due to the dynamic specifics of the development of the field of commercialization of blockchain technologies. (18)

A direct analysis of the existing rules for the taxation of cryptocurrencies in foreign countries showed a number of similarities and differences in the implementation of the tax and legal regulation of the relations in question.

Taxes on income, profits and capital gains (according to the OECD classification) dominate as the main fiscal instrument; at the same time, in some countries (the Netherlands) there is an alternative approach - the application of property taxes using the legal structure of fictitious (imputed) income.

Capital gains taxes (OECD classification) are used by most of the countries studied to tax income from the sale of cryptocurrencies. (17)

At the same time, it is conditionally possible to single out different trends in the nature of such regulation: identification with the current rules for the taxation of capital assets (USA); allocation as a separate type of property from traditional capital (Germany); exemption from capital gains tax (Portugal). In addition, some jurisdictions (Singapore) generally lack capital gains taxation mechanisms (which also applies to investments in cryptocurrencies).

Special attention deserves the approach existing in a number of countries (Singapore, Portugal) to distinguish between investment and entrepreneurial activities of individuals for the purpose of taxing transactions with cryptocurrency.

At the same time, as an alternative, it is worth highlighting mechanisms similar in meaning, but different in the way of implementation, for dividing investments into short-term and long-term ones (USA, Germany). Both of these approaches combine the goals of stimulating investment and implementing the principles of economic feasibility and tax fairness.

The above conclusions largely give an idea of the emerging vector of legal regulation of the issues under consideration in the world. Being one of the most striking examples of the digital transformation of the economy, cryptocurrency poses a number of fundamental legal issues for the legislator. And in our opinion, further research and systematization of the experience of foreign countries can be extremely useful both for solving such general issues and for developing effective rules for taxing cryptocurrency and other digital assets within the framework of domestic legislation on taxes and fees.

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IMPORT SUBSTITUTION POTENTIAL OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

For more than 30 years of independence, the Republic of Kazakhstan has not yet reached a high level of self-sufficiency in the production of products and goods for the population. On the shelves of the country you can see many imported goods. As a result, the constant growth of imports has a negative impact on domestic inflation. So, for the period from 2017 to 2022, imports to Kazakhstan increased by 69%. The share of imports in the domestic market is significant for a number of goods. Inflation growth in Kazakhstan in January 2023 in annual terms increased to 20.7%. In December 2022, there was an increase to 20.3%. Over the year, food prices increased by 25.7%, non-food products rose by 20.2%, and the cost of paid services increased by 14.2%. There is a need to implement an import substitution program that will improve the situation with economic security (self-sufficiency of the domestic market, including food) and reduce the growth of domestic inflation. The analysis of the import substitution potential in the Republic of Kazakhstan was carried out. Attention is focused on the direction in which the state and other interested parties need to move to solve the problem of import substitution without opening new industries.

Keywords: Import substitution, inflation, import, export, prices, Kazakhstan.

During the period of a decline in prices on the world market for raw materials, the emergence of problems in international transportation due to the current difficult geopolitical situation, the macroeconomic indicators of Kazakhstan decreased significantly, which affected the economic condition of entrepreneurs and the population. In addition, the country's accession to the EAEU and the WTO has significantly reduced the competitiveness of enterprises in the local market.

These factors have led to a constant increase in imports and rising inflation, which, in turn, leads to a

slowdown in the country's economic growth and a decrease in the purchasing power of the population. Therefore, the issue of import substitution for the development of the economy of Kazakhstan acquired particular relevance 10 years ago.

So, for the period from 2017 to 2022, imports to Kazakhstan increased by 69%. Of these, there is an increase in the following consumer goods as food products - 61%, drinks - 138%, clothing - 234%, cars, trailers and semi-trailers - 201%, pharmaceutical products - 80%, agricultural products - 93 %.

Table 1.

Export and import of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2017-2022

Index	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Export, thousand US dollars	48 503 260	61 111 221	58 065 589	47 540 773	60 321 024	84 393 977
Import, thousand US dollars	29 599 629	33 658 519	39 709 306	38 929 076	41 415 435	50 043 643

Source: Bureau of National Statistics of Republic of Kazakhstan

The share of imports in the domestic market is significant for a number of goods. For example, according to the Bureau of National Statistics of Republic of Kazakhstan (BNS RK), in 2022 the following values were recorded for some commodity items: processed and canned vegetables - 78.3%, margarine and similar products - 49%, milk in solid form - 77.1%, cheese and

cottage cheese - 48.7%, sugar - 49.2%, yarn and sewing threads - 68%, blankets and blankets - 95.2%, outerwear - 99.4%, clothes and clothing accessories for babies - 97.6%, shoes - 95.8%, soap and organic surface-active substances and preparations for use as soap - 67.3%, detergents - 95.5%, tires - 100%.